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SIZE-EXCLUSION CHROMATOGRAPHY OF SOME POLYSACCHARIDE DERIVATIVES FROM NATURAL SOURCES

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Abstract:

Objective. In the article molar mass and structural properties some of natural polysaccharides and their derivatives were studied by Size-exclusion chromatography.

Methods. For investigation of electrostatic and polyelectrolyte properties of natural polysaccharides Exclusion liquid chromatography method was used.

Results. Polyelectrolyte and electrostatic effects of polysaccharide derivatives in Size-exclusion chromatography were suppressed by using of aqueous eluent containing salt solution.

Conclusion. As a result of the research, it was shown that many of polysaccharides are polyelectrolytes and determination of their molar mass parameters is complicated by electrostatic effects in Size-exclusion chromatography.

Key words: polysaccharides, carboxymethyl chitosan, galactomannan, exclusion chromatography, heparin, electrostatic effects, polyelectrolytes.

Introduction. Water-soluble derivatives of polysaccharides are widely used due to a wide range of their useful and unique properties in biomedicine, pharmaceuticals, cosmetology, agriculture, and other fields. Biologically active polysaccharides from natural raw materials include chitosan, carrageenan, arabinogalactan (AG), heparin, agar, fucoidan, etc. Agar and carrageenan are obtained by extraction from red and fucoidan from brown seaweeds, and the chains of green algae polysaccharide molecules have a heterogeneous structure with sugar residues, such as glucuronoxylogamannans, glucuronoxylo-

rhamnogalactans, and xyloarabinogalactans [1, 2]. They are considered potential biologically active substances and have immunomodulatory, antitumor, antiviral, and antibacterial properties [3]. The most widely used anticoagulant drug in modern medical practice is the natural glycosaminoglycan heparin, however, the use of heparin causes some side effects, such as bleeding, and heparin-induced thrombocytopenia. The anticoagulant activity of sulfated polysaccharides

depends on the method of sulfation, which affects the degree of sulfation, the nature, and location of sulfate groups, molecular weight, etc. Many sulfated polysaccharides have a variety of biological activities, including anticoagulant, antithrombotic, antiviral, and antibacterial. [4-8]. Plant polysaccharides such as pullulan, galactan, galactomannan, and fucoidan sulfates have anticoagulant activity [9–13]. This article discusses the physicochemical and molecular weight characteristics of polysaccharides and their derivatives determined by the method of Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC).

It is known from a few literature sources [10, 13] that sulfated derivatives of AG have hypolipidemic and anticoagulant activity. In the laboratory of natural synthons and ligands of the Irkutsk Institute of Chemistry, named after A.E. Favorsky Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, sulfated AG was obtained in the form of a potassium salt by sulfating AG with the SO₃-dimethylformamide complex in dimethyl sulfoxide [11, 12]. In preliminary preclinical studies, the drug proved to be a promising lipid-lowering agent with a pronounced anticoagulant effect [14–17]. A relatively small number of works [18, 22] have been devoted to the study and determination of the molar mass of AG. Thus, in [18], the molecular weight distribution (MWD) of larch AG samples was determined by the SEC method on an Agilent 1200 chromatograph with a 1260 Infinity refractometric detector (30°C), PL Aquagel-OH 40 300 × 7.5 mm, 0.1 M LiNO₃, and 1 mL/min). The column was calibrated using standard samples of dextran (Sigma-Aldrich) with molecular masses of 10600, 20000, 41272, and 70000 Da. As the feedstock, we used AG obtained by the original method [18] from Siberian larch wood (*Larix sibirica* Ledeb.). The infrared spectra and MWD of arabinogalactan sulfates in the form of sodium and ammonium salts, obtained using various sulfating reagents, were compared. According to the data obtained,

the investigated sulfated derivatives and the initial samples of AG differ noticeably in terms of hydrogen bonds and molar mass distribution. In [23], the synthesis of guar gum sulfates by a complex of sulfur trioxide with 1,4-dioxane was studied. It is shown that the following optimal conditions for sulfation of guar gum with sulfur trioxide-1,4-dioxane complex were established: temperature 60 °C, duration 2.9 h, and volume of chlorosulfonic acid 3.1 ml. The presence of sulfate groups in the structure of guar gum was confirmed by elemental analysis and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). Sulfated guar gum has also been characterized by X-ray diffraction analysis, scanning electron microscopy, and gel chromatography. From gel chromatography data, it was shown that during the sulfation of guar gum with a sulfur trioxide complex with 1,4-dioxane, the molecular weight decreases from 600 to 176 kDa.

Sulfated derivatives of the galactomannan family have a variety of biological activities. In [24], sulfated galactomannan was obtained from fenugreek gum in a chlorosulfonic acid/pyridine medium. To obtain derivatives with the highest degree of substitution (DS), the optimal conditions for sulfation were determined in the experiment according to the Box-Behnken scheme. Analysis of the quadratic regression model confirmed that reaction time was the most significant DS exposure parameter. Under the chosen conditions, the maximum value of the degree of sulfation was obtained at 0.490. The results of FT-IR and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) showed the presence of the SO₃- group. In ¹³C NMR spectroscopy, the original C-6 peaks did not completely disappear, and new peaks appeared at δ 63.2 and 64.0, illustrating incomplete substitution, predominantly in the C-6 position. After sulfation, Size exclusion chromatography combined with polygonal laser light scattering (SEC-MALLS) found that the average molecular

weight (Mw) of the sulfated derivatives rapidly decreased. The introduction of negatively charged SO_3^- groups into the electrostatic interaction and the decrease in MM could have a significant effect on its biological activity [24].

The extraction of carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCHT) from chitosan (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was carried out as follows. 1.0 g of chitosan was mixed in 25 ml of isopropyl alcohol for 10 minutes at room temperature, and 8 ml of 40% NaOH was added to the suspension. As a result, the suspension was brought to a standstill. After that, another 35 ml of isopropyl alcohol was added to the solution and stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature. After mixing the suspension well, adding 5 g of monochloroacetic acid, the temperature of the solution was raised to

450 °C and stirred for 3 hours. After that, the solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. After filtration, it was washed with 200 ml of methanol. Then, the sediment was removed from the filter paper and put into a 200 ml beaker, 100 ml of methanol was poured over it, and 10 drops of acetic acid were added. It was covered with foil and stirred at room temperature for 14 hours. Mixing was stopped, and the solution was cooled for 10 minutes. Then the solution was filtered, and the filter was washed with ethyl alcohol 3–4 times. A small sample was taken and dissolved in water to check solubility. The pH value of the dissolved solution was determined to be neutral. The resulting wet precipitate was dried at 500 °C for 12–14 hours and weighed 2.1 grams.

SEC analysis of synthesized CMCHT was carried out in water (Fig. 1a and 2a)

Fig.1

Fig.2

Elution chromatograms of carboxymethyl chitosan from Shandong Yinuokang

Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd (China) (Fig.1) and from Black Sea crab (Turkey) (Fig.2). and salt solutions as eluent (Fig.1 b and 2b). Figures 1 and 2, respectively, show the chromatograms of CMCHT obtained from chitosan synthesized by the Chinese Shandong Yinuokang Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. and CMCHT

synthesized by modifying chitin, extracted from the shell of the Black Sea crab (Turkey). The chromatograms presented in Figures 1a and 2a were recorded when water was used as an eluent in SEC, and we can see that the properties of CMCHT molecules describe the polyelectrolyte expansion effect, i.e., the reduction of the

elution time and the multimodal appearance of the elution curves. The reason for this is that, due to the ionization of the carboxyl groups in the CMCHT chain in water, anions move away from each other under the influence of Coulomb forces, that is, macromolecules grow in geometric size. This phenomenon is called the polyelectrolyte expansion effect. Chromatographic peaks with small values occur due to the increase in the size of macromolecules and their early exit from the column before being able to enter the pores on the surface of the sorbent. This anomalous phenomenon was eliminated when a solution of NaNO_3 in water with a concentration of 0.1 mol/l was used as an eluent. As a result of the screening (blocking) of anionic groups by Na^+ ions in water, the forces of electrostatic interaction decrease, and the polymer chain becomes neutral. In this case, the elution time corresponding to the peaks of the chromatograms increases, and the symmetry of the chromatograms becomes visible. This situation indicates that the molecular sieve separation mechanism of

SEC is activated (Figures 1b and 2b). As can be seen from Figures 1b and 2b, the samples consist of 4 and 3 fractions, respectively. Fractions 1, 2, 3 in Figure 1 b belong to the CMCHT sample, and peak 4 belongs to the solvent. In Fig. 2b, it was found that fractions 1, 2 belong to CMCHT, and peak 3 belongs to the solvent. SEC was used to study the polyelectrolytic nature and determine the average molecular weights of commercial unfractionated heparin "Heparin-Indar" (Ukraine) and low molecular weight heparin Clexane (Sanofi, France). SEC was performed on an Agilent 1260 Infinity high speed liquid chromatograph (USA) with a refractive index detector. The eluent flow rate was 0.8 ml/min. The volume of the injected sample was 25 μl . Figure 3 shows combined gel chromatograms of low molecular weight heparin brand "Clexane"(SANOFI-AVENTIS FRANCE), obtained at different concentrations of the injected sample in water (curves 1,2, 3) and in an aqueous solution of 0.1 M NaNO_3 (curve 4).

Fig.3. Overlapped chromatograms of heparin "Clexane" in water (1,2,3) and salt solution (0.1M NaNO_3) (4). Concentrations at peaks, g/dl: 1 – 0.05; 2 -0,1; 3-0.2

It can be seen from the figure that, without the addition of neutral salt or water, the chromatograms have asymmetric shapes, and the retained volumes (or elution time) decrease with decreasing

polymer concentration in the solution, which characterizes the presence of the polyelectrolyte swelling effect in the chromatographic system. With the use of an aqueous solution having the neutral salt

(NaNO_3) with a concentration of 0.1 mol/l as an eluent, electrostatic effects were eliminated. It can be seen from Fig.4, where separation of two commercial heparins: Heparin-Indar (Ukraine) and low molar mass heparin “Clexane”.

Fig.4. Overlapped chromatograms of Heparin-Indar (M=15 kDa) (1) and low molar mass heparin “Clexane” (M=4.5 kDa) (2)

Note that the suppression of the electrostatic effects of the samples during the SEC process occurs due to the screening of the Coulomb repulsive forces of sulfate groups in the chains of heparin molecules due to the presence of NaNO_3 salt in water.

Conclusion. In the SEC of anionic polysaccharides, such as carboxymethyl chitosan and heparin, the separation

mechanism in pure water as eluent is distorted by the polyelectrolyte expansion effect. In these cases, elution profiles of chromatograms will have an asymmetric form, and retention times (volumes) will decrease at small concentrations of injected solutes. In eluent containing 0.1 moles/l of NaNO_3 , electrostatic effects were suppressed.

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C O N T E N T S

PRIMARY PROCESSING OF COTTON, TEXTILE AND LIGHT INDUSTRY

A.Shodmonkulov, R.Jamolov, X.Yuldashev	
Analysis of load changes in the chain drive during the drying process of cotton falling from the longitudinal shelves of the drum.....	3
A.Xomidjonov	
Influence and characteristics of drying mechanisms in leather production on the derma layer.....	8
J.Monnopov, J.Kayumov, N.Maksudov	
Analysis of elastic fabrics for compression sportswear in the new assortment	13
S.Matismailov, K.Matmuratova, Sh.Korabayev, A.Yuldashev	
Investigation of the influence of speed modes of the combined drum on the quality indicators of the tape.....	18
A.Shodmonkulov, K.Jumaniyazov, R.Jamolov, X.Yuldashev	
Determination of the geometric and kinematic parameters of the developed chain gear for the 2SB-10 dryer.....	23
R.Jamolov, A.Shodmonkulov, X.Yuldashev	
Determination of dryer drum moisture extraction depending on its operating modes.....	27
A.Djuraev, K.Yuldashev, O.Teshaboyev	
Theoretical studies on screw conveyor for transportation and cleaning of linter and design of constructive parameters of transmissions.....	29
S.Khashimov, Kh.Isakhanov, R.Muradov	
Creation of technology and equipment for improved cleaning of cotton from small impurities.....	36
G.Juraeva, R.Muradov	
The process of technical grades of medium staple cotton at gin factories and its analysis.....	40
I.Xakimjonov	
Literature analysis on the research and development of the method of designing special clothes for workers of metal casting and metal processing enterprises.....	44
GROWING, STORAGE, PROCESSING AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS AND FOOD TECHNOLOGIES	
A.Khodjiev, A.Choriev, U.Raximov	
Improving the technology of production of functional nutrition juices.....	49
U.Nishonov	
Research in beverage technology intended to support the functions of the cardiovascular system.....	53

Z.Vokkosov, S.Hakimov	
Development of new types of vegetable juices and beverages technology...	59
CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGIES	
M.Latipova	
Analysis of the current status of thermoelectric materials and technology for obtaining and manufacturing half-elements.....	66
G.Ochilov, I.Boymatov, N.Ganiyeva	
Physico-chemical properties of activated adsorbents based on logan bentonite.....	72
U.Nigmatov	
Simulation of heat transfer process in absorber channels.....	77
T.Abduxakimov, D.Sherkuziev	
Procurement of local raw materials complex fertilizers with nitrogen-phosphate-potassium containing moisture.....	84
P.Tojiyev, X.Turaev, G.Nuraliyev, A.Djalilov	
Study of the structure and properties of polyvinyl chloride filled with bazalt mineral.....	89
M.Yusupov	
Investigation of phthalocyanine diamidophosphate- copper by thermal analysis.....	95
L.Oripova, P.Xayitov, A.Xudayberdiyev	
Testing new activated coals AU-T and AU-K from local raw materials when filtration of the waste mdea at gazlin gas processing plant.....	101
N.Kurbanov, D.Rozikova	
Based on energy efficient parameters of fruit drying chamber devices for small enterprises.....	107
Sh.Xakimov, M.Komoliddinov	
Basic methods and technological schemes for obtaining vegetable oils.....	113
A.Boimirzaev, Z.Kamolov	
Size-exclusion chromatography of some polysaccharide derivatives from natural sources.....	117
MECHANICS AND ENGINEERING	
U.Erkaboev, N.Sayidov	
Dependence of the two-dimensional combined density of states on the absorbing photon energy in GaAs/AlGaAs at quantizing magnetic field.....	124
I.Siddikov, A.Denmumaxamadiyev, S.A'zamov	
Investigation of electromagnetic current transformer performance characteristics for measuring and controlling the reactive power dissipation of a short-circuited rotor synchronous motor.....	136
Sh.Kudratov	
Evaluation and development of diagnostics of the crankshaft of diesel locomotives.....	141

Z.Khudoykulov, I.Rakhmatullaev	
A new key stream encryption algorithm and its cryptanalysis.....	146
T.Mominov, D.Yuldoshev	
Coordination of the movement of transport types in areas with high passenger flow.....	157
R.Abdullayev, M.Azambayev, S.Baxritdinov	
Analysis of research results according to international standards.....	163
R.Abdullayev, M.Azambayev	
Cotton fiber rating, innovation current developments, prospects for cooperation of farms and clusters.....	168
F.Dustova, S.Babadzhanov.	
Calculation of the load on the friction clutch of the sewing machine.....	174
Z.Vafayeva, J.Matyakubova, M.Mansurova	
Improvement of the design of the shuttle drum in the sewing machine.....	179
A.Obidov, M.Vokhidov	
Preparation of a new structure created for sorting of ginning seeds.....	185
Sh.Mamajanov	
Carrying out theoretical studies of the cotton regenerator.....	192
ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION	
A.Khojaev	
Methodological issues of organizing internal audits and control of off-budget funds in higher education institutions.....	199
I.Nosirov	
Theoretical foundations of establishing new technologies on personal management system.....	203
Z.Mamakhanova, D.Ormonova	
Specific characteristics of uzbek national art of embroidery.....	209
A.Raximov, M.Khusainov, M.Turgunpulatov, S.Khusainov, A.Gaybullayev	
Energy-saving modes of the heat treatment of concrete.....	213
ECONOMICAL SCIENCES	
M.Bekmirzayev, J.Xolikov	
Prospects for the development of service industries.....	222
A.Ilyosov	
Organizational and economic mechanisms to support the export of industrial products: a comparative analysis of foreign experience and proposals.....	227
I.Foziljonov	
The importance of multiplier indicators in assessing the effectiveness of the cash flow of the enterprise.....	232
K.Kurpayanidi	
Innovative activity of business entities in the conditions of transformation: a retrospective analysis.....	238

Sh.Muxitdinov	
Main characteristics of the risk management mechanism in manufacturing enterprises.....	248
Y.Najmiddinov	
Green economy and green growth. initial efforts of sustainable development in Uzbekistan.....	252
E.Narzullayev	
The methods for measuring the effectiveness of social entrepreneurship activity.....	259
E.Narzullayev	
Analysis of the management and development of environmental social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.....	265
F.Bayboboeva	
Legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity.....	270
Z.Boltaeva	
Foundations of neuromarketing strategy in industry.....	276
R.Rashidov	
Issues of regional development of small business.....	281
Sh.Abdumurotov	
Methodology for forecasting the competitiveness of an enterprise based on the Elliott wave principle.....	288
S.Goyipnazarov	
Assessment of impact of artificial intelligence on labor market and human capital.....	299
A.Norov	
Evolution of management science.....	307
K.Narzullayev	
Investment process in the republic of Uzbekistan.....	317
Kh.Irismatov	
Statistical analysis of assessment of the volume of the hidden economy in the republic of Uzbekistan.....	322
